

Table S2. Taxa of chloroplast genomes downloaded from the GenBank and used in phylogenetic analysis.

	Subfamily	Tribe	Taxon	Accession No.
1	Amygdaloideae	Amygdaleae	<i>Prunus salicina</i> Lindl.	KY420002.1
2	Amygdaloideae	Kerrieae	<i>Coleogyne ramosissima</i> Torr.	KY419967.1
3	Amygdaloideae	Kerrieae	<i>Neviusia cliffonii</i> Shevock, Ertter & D. W. Taylor	KY419980.1
4	Amygdaloideae	Lyonothamneae	<i>Lyonothamnus floribundus</i> A. Gray	KY420005.1
5	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Gillenia stipulata</i> (Muhl. ex Willd.) Nutt.	KY419996.1
6	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Kageneckia crataegifolia</i> Lindl.	KY420027.1
7	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Vauquelinia californica</i> (Torr.) Sarg.	KY419925.1
8	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Amelanchier sinica</i> (C. K. Schneid.) Chun	KY419998.1
9	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Aronia melanocarpa</i> (Michx.) Elliott	KY420007.1
10	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Chaenomeles japonica</i> (Thunb.) Lindl. ex Spach	KT932966.1
11	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Chamaemeles coriacea</i> Lindl.	DQ860454.1
12	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Cornus domestica</i> (L.) Spach	KY419956.1
13	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Crataegus pinnatifida</i> var. <i>major</i> N. E. Br.	KY419945.1
14	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i> Mill.	KX499857.1
15	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Dichotomanthes tristanii</i> Kurz	KY420031.1
16	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Docynia doumeri</i> (Bois) C. K. Schneid.	KX499861.1
17	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Docyniopsis tschonoskii</i> (Maxim.) Koidz.	KX499863.1
18	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Eriobotrya bengalensis</i> var. <i>angustifolia</i> Cardot	KY419922.1
19	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Eriobotrya japonica</i> (Thunb.) Lindl.	KT633951.1
20	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Eriolobus yunnanensis</i> (Franch.) C. K. Schneid.	MH394387.1
21	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Heteromeles arbutifolia</i> Greene	KY419965.1
22	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malacomeles denticulata</i> (Kunth) G. N. Jones	KY419982.1
23	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malus x prunifolia</i> (Willd.) Borkh.	KU851961.1
24	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malus baccata</i> (L.) Borkh.	KX499859.1
25	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malus domestica</i> Borkh.	KY818915.1
26	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malus hupehensis</i> (Pamp.) Rehder	MK020147.1
27	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malus micromalus</i> Makino	MF062434.1
28	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Malus transitoria</i> (Batalin) C. K. Schneid.	MK098838.1
29	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Mespilus canescens</i> J.B.Phipps	KY420022.1
30	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Micromeles alnifolia</i> (Siebold & Zucc.) Koehne	KY420010.1
31	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Micromeles rhamnoides</i> Decne.	KY419962.1
32	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Osteomeles anthyllidifolia</i> (Sm.) Lindl.	KY419940.1
33	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Peraphyllum ramosissimum</i> Nutt. ex Torr. & A.Gray	KY420011.1
34	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Photinia integrifolia</i> Lindl.	KY419933.1
35	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Photinia prionophylla</i> (Franch.) C. K. Schneid.	KY419946.1
36	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Pourthiaea arguta</i> var. <i>salicifolia</i> (Decne.) Hook. f.	KY419919.1
37	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Pseudocydonia sinensis</i> (Thouin) C. K. Schneid.	KT932967.1
38	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i> M. Roem.	KY420030.1
39	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i> (Burm.f.) Nakai	AP012207.1
40	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Rhaphiolepis umbellata</i> (Thunb.) Makino	KY419931.1
41	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Eriolobus florentina</i> (Zuccagni) Stapf	KX499856.1
42	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Sorbus helena</i> Koehne	KY419924.1
43	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Sorbus rufopilosa</i> C.K.Schneid.	KY419990.1
44	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Sorbus trilobata</i> (Labill. ex Poir.) Heynh.	KX499858.1
45	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Sorbus ulleungensis</i> Chin S. Chang	MG011706.1
46	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Stranvaesia davidiana</i> Decne.	KY420003.1
47	Amygdaloideae	Maleae	<i>Torninaria clusii</i> M. Roem.	KY457242.1
48	Amygdaloideae	Sorbarieae	<i>Adenostoma fasciculatum</i> Hook. & Arn.	KY387915.1
49	Amygdaloideae	Sorbarieae	<i>Chamaebatiaria millefolium</i> (Torr.) Maxim.	KY420017.1
50	Amygdaloideae	Spiraeae	<i>Holodiscus discolor</i> (Pursh) Maxim.	KY420032.1
51	Amygdaloideae	Spiraeae	<i>Kelseya uniflora</i> Rydb.	KY419988.1
52	Amygdaloideae	Spiraeae	<i>Luetkea pectinata</i> (Pursh) Kuntze	KY419971.1
53	Amygdaloideae	Spiraeae	<i>Pentactina rupicola</i> Nakai	JQ041763.1
54	Amygdaloideae	Spiraeae	<i>Pterophyllum caespitosum</i> (Nutt. ex Torr. & A. Gray) Rydb.	KY419970.1
55	Dryadoideae	Dryadeae	<i>Cercocarpus montanus</i> var. <i>minutiflorus</i> (Abrams) F. L. Martin	KY420024.1
56	Dryadoideae	Dryadeae	<i>Chamaebatia foliolosa</i> Benth.	KY419950.1
57	Dryadoideae	Dryadeae	<i>Purshia tridentata</i> (Pursh) DC.	KY420000.1
58	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Acaena pinnatifida</i> Ruiz & Pav.	KY419984.1
59	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Agrimonia pilosa</i> Ledeb.	KY419942.1
60	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Bencomia exstipulata</i> Svent.	MG682353.1
61	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Cliffortia repens</i> Schltr.	KY419983.1
62	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Dendriopoterium menendezii</i> Svent.	KY419966.1
63	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Hagenia abyssinica</i> (Bruce ex Steud.) J. F. Gmel.	KX008604.1
64	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Leucosidea sericea</i> Eckl. & Zeyh.	KY419929.1
65	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Margyricarpus pinnatus</i> (Lam.) Kuntze	KY419972.1
66	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Polylepis reticulata</i> Hieron.	KY419921.1
67	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Poterium spinosum</i> L.	KY419948.1
68	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i> L.	KY419975.1
69	Rosoideae	Agrimoniaeae	<i>Spenceria ramalana</i> Trimen	KY419995.1
70	Rosoideae	Colurieae	<i>Fallugia paradoxa</i> (D. Don) Endl. ex Torr.	KY419999.1
71	Rosoideae	Colurieae	<i>Geum elatum</i> Wall. ex G. Don	KY419976.1
72	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Alchemilla pectinata</i> Kunth	KY419937.1
73	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Chamaerhodos erecta</i> (L.) Bunge	KY420001.1
74	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Comarum salesovianum</i> (Stephan) Asch. & Graebn.	KY420034.1
75	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Dasiphora fruticosa</i> (L.) Rydb.	MF683841.1
76	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Drymocalis glandulosa</i> (Lindl.) Rydb.	KY420015.1
77	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Fragaria orientalis</i> Losinsk.	KY769126.1
78	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Potaninia mongolica</i> Maxim.	KY419959.1
79	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Potentilla indica</i> (Jacks.) Th. Wolf	KY420014.1
80	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Sibbaldia procumbens</i> L.	KY419935.1
81	Rosoideae	Potentilleae	<i>Sibbaldianthe sericea</i> Grubov	KY419993.1